

A Dual Function Metasurface Based on Aluminium Gallium Arsenide PIN Diodes

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Abstract—A dual function metasurface based on flip-chip Aluminium Gallium Arsenide (AlGaAs) PIN diodes is presented. Depending on the biasing state of the PIN diodes, the metasurface exhibits either a 1-bit reflection response or a transmission response. The design was optimized using the full 3D model of the AlGaAs PIN diodes. Simulations have been carried out using CST microwave studio to evaluate the performance of the dual function metasurface. The optimized metasurface demonstrates an average reflection loss of 0.3 dB and a transmission loss of 1.09 dB at 29 GHz. The corresponding simulation results were compared against both the simulated (obtained from a SPICE model developed in a circuit simulator) and measured S-parameters of the diodes. The transmission and reflection responses obtained at the operating frequency remain consistent across the three modelling approaches are presented and discussed.

Index Terms—PIN diode, reconfigurable metasurface, reflection, transmission, unit cell.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in the number of mobile communications users and the requirement of increased throughput requires the development of a new generation of wireless communication operating in the mm-Wave and beyond. Over the last decade, seeking solutions to mitigate the higher propagation losses of mm-Wave has been a hot topic among researchers [1], [2]. Although highly directive massive MIMO is an outstanding method to alleviate the path loss as well as improving the

channel capacity, MIMOs are usually power hungry systems [1], [3]. Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) and intelligent reflective surface (IRS) concepts have emerged as a potential solution to enhance received signal in urban areas [4].

Fundamentally, RISs are composed of many reconfigurable subwavelength elements. Reconfigurability may pertain to the control of the amplitude, phase, or polarization of the impinging wave. There are several methods which have been reported in the literature in order to obtain the tunability. Liquid crystal technology is one of the possible methods to obtain continuous tunability as it offers a low-cost efficient solution [4]. However, it suffers from slow response time and temperature dependent response [5]. Although it has been discovered that the response time can be reduced by applying positive and negative bias voltages in pixelated grating electrode geometry, it is still slower than other possible methods such as semiconductors and MEMS based designs [6]. MEMS-actuated mirror technology on the other hand, is capable of achieving tens of μs response time, however it is not suitable for low THz range due to the displacement limit of the technology [5], [7]. As a semiconductor alternative, varactor diodes can achieve faster tuning speeds (i.e., $<1\mu\text{s}$) while maintaining a continuous variation. Despite the response time, they are more lossy at the mm-Wave range and require a

complex biasing network to attain the necessary analog voltage [8]. In contrast to varactor diodes, PIN diodes show a low-loss feature at the mm-Wave range and can be biased with an FPGA instead of complex analog circuitry, which makes PIN diodes a much more promising candidate compared to other technologies [8].

GaAs based PIN diodes operate mainly in two states (i.e., when the diode is forward biased, also referred as ON state and when the diode is reverse biased, also referred as OFF state) although there are different states depending on the bias current and voltage [9]. They often show inductive behaviour due to the package in the ON state, while they become capacitive in the OFF state because of the junction capacitance and the parasitic capacitance as a result of the package [9], [10]. Different equivalent circuit models of PIN diodes have been proposed over the years. In fact, the equivalent circuit model should be a combination of both extrinsic and intrinsic parts. The extrinsic part is related with the effect of the external factors such as feed line, whereas the intrinsic part is the effect of the junction [9]. GaAs based PIN diodes, similar to the other semiconductor devices, exhibit a frequency dependant behavior, hence the equivalent model depends on the frequency of operation.

In this study, a reconfigurable unit cell for a dual function metasurface is presented. The two main responses are transmission and reflection. The reflection response consists of two states, which are separated by a 180° phase shift. The function of the unit cell can be controlled by two AlGaAs PIN diodes. Furthermore, different modelling techniques of PIN diodes are presented and discussed.

II. UNIT CELL

The unit cell of the proposed periodic metasurface has two layers, each having a PIN diode. A section of the metasurface containing 3-by-3 unit cells is depicted in Fig. 1. The top layer includes two different size rectangular patches connected by the first PIN diode, while the bottom layer has two identical U-shaped patches connected by the second PIN diode. The unit cell is illustrated in Fig. 1 by dotted squares. For the optimum operation of the dual function metasurface each diode on the bottom layer must be precisely aligned with its counterpart on the top layer, such that their positions coincide in the xy -plane. Misaligned diode pairs may result in increased reflection losses if the 1-bit reflection response is desired.

Both layers are etched on a 0.79 mm-thick TLY-5 substrate, which has a dielectric constant of 2.2 and a loss tangent of 0.0009 at 10 GHz. The unit cell is a 5 mm square. Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b indicate the dimensions of the top and the bottom layers of a single unit cell, respectively. Besides, the corresponding dimensions are presented in Table I.

Each PIN diode used in the unit cell is a MADP-000907-14020P, which is a flip chip PIN diode supplied by Macom. The chip has a maximum length of 0.765 mm, which equals the separation between patches on each layer. The contacts of the diodes are connected to the patches by microstrip lines

Fig. 1. a) Top view of the dual function metasurface, b) Bottom view of the dual function metasurface

Fig. 2. a) Top view of the unit cell, b) Bottom view of the unit cell, c) Side view of then unit cell

underneath the chip. The diodes are centred on each layer, and they are aligned as illustrated in Fig. 2c.

The states of the unit cell depending on the diodes' conditions are given in Table II. The diode located between U-shaped patches controls the main function of the unit cell, which is either transmission or reflection. The second diode located in between two different size rectangular patches is exploited to achieve a phase shift of 180° when the unit cell is operating as a reflector. Nevertheless, the transmission state

TABLE I
DIMENSIONS OF THE UNIT CELL IN MM.

$L1_a+L1_b$	2.5	L3	2
W1	4.4	W3	1.6
L2	0.4	A3	2
W2	3.6	B3	1.8

TABLE II
OPERATION STATES OF THE UNIT CELL ACCORDING TO THE BIAS
CONDITIONS OF THE DIODES

State	1st diode	2nd diode
1	Forward Biased	Reverse Biased
0	Reverse Biased	Reverse Biased
TX	Forward Biased	Forward Biased
Undefined	Reverse Biased	Forward Biased

can be affected by both diodes. When the second diode is reverse biased, the unit cell behaves as if it is a 1-bit reflector where the reflection phase depends on the bias condition of the 1st diode. State “1” is where the unit cell is operating as a reflector and creates 180° phase shift compared to State “0”. If both diodes are forward biased, the unit cell acts as a transmitter, which is State “TX”. In addition to these three operating states, there is one more possible bias configuration when the 1st diode is reverse biased and the 2nd diode is forward biased, that is State “Undefined”. The unit cell shows neither transmissive nor reflective behaviour in that state.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulations were carried out on a computing system with Intel Xeon Gold 5416S CPU @ 2.0 GHz, 256 GB of RAM and NVIDIA RTX A5500 GPU. The afore mentioned unit cell with different diode models were simulated under periodic boundary conditions with the frequency domain solver of CST Microwave Studio. The electric field orientation of the incident wave is along y-axis. The simulations were performed under normal incidence as illustrated in the Fig. 2c.

Fig. 3. Reflection and transmission coefficients of the unit cell modelled with 3D-EM

Metamaterial design with PIN diodes is challenging due to the fact that the effect of the PIN diode is challenging to calculate. In fact, the effect is a combination of the internal reactance, resistance and coupling between unit cell and the diode. Therefore, the effect of the PIN diode is

different for each unit cell. Nevertheless, various studies have proposed different equivalent models consisting of an RLC circuit for PIN diodes [9], [10]. However, the response of a simple RLC circuit is narrowband and frequency dependant. A more accurate alternative is the use of S-parameters of the diodes as extracted by circuit simulators (Spice model) [11]. Another recommended approach is the use of the measured S-parameters of the diode. The dual function metasurface was optimized with the use of the 3D model (3D-EM) of the diode. Additionally, in this paper, we compare the measured S-parameters (MS) with the circuit simulator based simulated S-parameters (CSMS), where the diodes are modeled either as edge lumped elements (ELEs) or face lumped elements (FLEs). Finally, we make a comparison between these modeling approaches and 3D-EM of the diode.

As mentioned above, the dual function operation of the metasurface was optimized at 29 GHz by simulating with 3D-EM of the diode. The transmission and reflection response of the unit cell is given in Fig. 3. The average loss of the unit cell between 28 GHz and 30 GHz is 0.61 dB in State “1”, 0.15 dB in State “0” and 1.08 dB in State “TX”. The phase of each reflection state is given in Fig. 4. The bandwidth where the phase difference is $180 \pm 12^\circ$ is between 27.75 GHz and 30 GHz, which is greater than 2 GHz and corresponds to slightly better than 7% fractional bandwidth around 27.875 GHz.

Fig. 5 compares the response of the unit cell in three different states with the different simulation techniques of the PIN diode. With the use of the 3D-EM of the diode in simulations, the center frequency in State “1” is 29 GHz which corresponds to the frequency used for unit cell optimization. If the diodes are modeled as ELEs, the frequency at which the maximum reflection coefficient occurs is moved to around 19 GHz although the unit cell was designed at 29 GHz. It is worth mentioning that the reflection coefficients obtained by both MS and CSMS data are in agreement. When the diodes are modeled as FLEs, the frequency region where the reflection

Fig. 4. Reflection phase of both states

Fig. 5. Simulation results of the unit cell with different approaches: a) in State "1", b) in State "0", c) in State "TX".

coefficient is more than 1 dB broadens slightly and is shifted to around 23 GHz. However, the reflection coefficient at 29 GHz remains unacceptable, even though the frequency of maximum reflection moves closer to 29 GHz. These frequency shifts are caused by the differences between these modelling approaches. While ELEs are distributed lumped element along an edge, FLEs are distributed along a face. The 3D-EM, on the other hand, creates the junction with the actual materials.

In State "0", a similar discrepancy in operating frequency

between the different models is observed as in State "1". Compared to the simulations with ELEs, modeling the diodes as FLEs results in a shift of the operating frequency region towards higher frequencies. Such frequency shifts are observed in simulations with both MS and CSMS data. The maximum reflection coefficient of the ELEs based simulations and FLEs based simulations occur around 24 GHz and 28 GHz respectively despite the unit cell being designed at 29 GHz. The reasons behind these frequency shifts are the same as in State "1". However, the amounts of frequency shifts between 3D-EM and lumped element based simulations are not the same in each state, which indicates that the biasing of the diodes affects the coupling between the unit cell and the diodes. Furthermore, a broadening of the frequency region where the reflection coefficient is more than 1 dB is observed in this state, analogous to the broadening in State "1".

On the other hand, in State "TX", the same frequency shift effect is present. Nevertheless, the unit cell shows good transmission characteristics above 22.5 GHz for all the aforementioned data and simulation techniques.

Fig. 6. Maximum of the magnitude of the surface current vectors of different methods when the unit cell working in State "TX".

As there is a significant discrepancy between the simulation approaches, a study about the surface currents was conducted. The ELE based approach models the PIN diodes as point to point lumped elements. This approach assumes that the predefined two points are connected by an infinitely thin wire, which leads to a high self-inductance. Instead, the diodes can be modeled as FLEs in order to reduce that self-inductance and increase the accuracy. Finally, the 3D-EM of the diode includes the same materials as the actual diode. This method has the impedance created by the materials instead of artificial lumped elements in the EM simulation software. Therefore, it takes into account not only the effect of the diode itself but also the coupling effect between the diode and the unit cell which leads to a more accurate surface current distribution on the unit cell.

Fig. 7. RMS value of the magnitude of the surface current vectors in State "TX" on the bottom layer; a) with ELE, b) with FLE, c) with 3D-EM

The unit cell was analyzed while it was operating in State "TX" in order to observe the surface currents. The simulated maximum of surface current vectors over frequency for different diode modeling approaches are illustrated in Fig. 6. Since the simulation results between the MS and the CSMS are similar, only the MS data was used for this study. In all methods, the maximum current occurs on the bottom surface where the second diode is located. The use of the 3D-EM of the diode enables an accurate representation of the localized high current densities within the diode structure, which are not captured by the artificial lumped element based approaches. This leads to a much higher maximum current density compared to the two other techniques. The RMS value

of the surface currents along the U-shaped patches at 29 GHz for all three simulation approaches are illustrated in Fig. 7. It can be seen that a thin wire is connecting two microstrip lines in Fig. 7a and a surface is connecting two microstrip lines in Fig. 7b. Moreover, Fig. 7c shows the surface currents of 3D-EM based simulation over the surface and over the metallic parts of the diode in the magnified circle. When the diodes are modeled as ELEs, the magnitude of the surface current vectors is distributed unevenly compared to the modeling as FLEs due to the fact that the FLE allows current to pass through thin wire. Furthermore, 3D-EM of the diode ensures the best performance in terms of the surface current distribution as expected. Although the maximum surface current of the ELE based simulation is higher than that of the FLE based simulation over the frequency region as shown in Fig. 6, the maximum surface current vector occurs at the end point of the ELE, besides FLE based simulation has higher surface current magnitude outside of the proximity of that end point as presented in Fig. 7.

IV. CONCLUSION

A reconfigurable metasurface containing two PIN diodes per periodic element is presented. The unit cell can operate either as a 1-bit reflector or as a transmitter depending on the bias conditions of the diodes. The 1-bit reflection mode has an average of 0.38 dB reflection loss, while the transmitter mode exhibits an average of 1.08 dB transmission loss across the operating frequency band.

The unit cell is analysed with three different simulation techniques for the AlGaAs PIN diodes and two sets of S-parameters. Additionally a study about the current density on the unit cell surface is conducted. The accuracy of the simulations will be verified by measurements in a future study.

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